

Validation Workshop

Internal documentation (T3.3)

Biodiversity Education

Eszter Kelemen¹, Kármén Czett¹

¹ ESSRG

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PLANET4B

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

List of abbreviations and acronyms

EU	European Union
TCS	Transformative Change Story
WS	Workshop
SB	Stakeholder Board

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Executive Summary

This report summarises the outcomes of the Validation Workshop of the Hungarian biodiversity education case held on 7 April 2025. The workshop was organised as part of the PLANET4B project (T3.3) and aimed to validate key findings/messages and to refine inputs/core messages for the 'Transformative Change Stories' with members of the stakeholder board. A total of 5 participants attended the workshop, three in-person and two online, including a teacher, a youth representative, and three environmental education experts. The workshop confirmed the main elements of the TCS and the recommendations developed for different types of actors. Workshop participants also highlighted that the TCS and the recommendations should have a broader framing going beyond school gardens as our research results are relevant for the school environment in general. Participants agreed that an infographic can be a good output but underlined the importance of better integrating scientific findings to our narrative change together with hyperlinks to detailed results.

Set-up of the Validation Workshop

The workshop was designed for 2 hours. This included a brief introduction, the presentation of the transformative change story and associated outputs, followed by an open discussion and finally a small reception.

Workshop Format

The workshop followed the format of open (informal) discussion. As two participants joined via Zoom, we presented the transformative change story through a few slides, visible both for the online and the in-person participants. During the discussion part one of us paid attention to the online participants and whenever they had a comment or question, we gave the word to them. The detailed agenda of the workshop is shared below.

Participant Selection

All nine members of the Stakeholder Board were invited. Three members joined in-person and two members online. Four members excused themselves due to international travel or other duties.

Validation Approach

Presentation and open discussion. While we let participants openly comment and challenge the TCS we presented to them, we also prepared some key questions through which we aimed to test the validity and robustness of our TCS, as well as its potential future use. These questions included:

- Do you think that the TCS presented here reflects well the findings of this case study? Does it align with your own experience / other research findings?
- Do you agree with the recommendations and the target groups selected for these recommendations? Should we cover a broader range of actors with the recommendations, e.g. parental communities or politicians?
- How could we ensure that this TCS has a policy impact? Is this output worth disseminating in policy circles?
- In which format and through which channels should we disseminate the TCS?

- o Visual output / infographic
- o Printed / online
- o Schools / existing networks / conferences

Context

PLANET4B project context

This was the fourth and final workshop with our stakeholder board – besides validating the TCS and discussing potential further collaborations, we also wanted to celebrate and thank the stakeholder board members for their voluntary contributions. The previous workshop was held in the autumn of 2024, where we already shared and discussed some of our results and brainstormed on recommendations (leverage points to change the educational system). Before the workshop we shared a written summary of the TCS and other materials prepared beforehand to enable participants to provide informed comments. Although this was our last meeting with the stakeholder board members, we agreed to stay in touch and collaborate along some other opportunities (e.g. contribute to the IUCN's collection on nature-based education which is co-edited by one of our board members).

Social context

The workshop was held at ESSRG's premises as it was easily approachable for all participants. Those who could not attend in-person were offered to join via Zoom. Despite this, unfortunately, only 5 out of the 9 SB members could join this workshop. Participants included 1 male and 4 female board members, one of them representing the young generation. The discussion was slightly dominated by those having an education expert background, while the teacher and the youth representatives were somewhat more silent. We tried to balance this by directly asking the more silent participants about their own viewpoints.

Institutional context

Participating board members had affiliations in schools or universities, only one of them (the youth representative) had affiliation in the private sector, and one of the board members was also affiliated with an international NGO. While the strong representation of the educational sector is beneficial from the point of view that the perspectives of the main target group of our TCS (schools and educational experts) could be captured, the lack of representation of the policy sector or local NGOs might risk that our recommendations are not fitted very well with the broader context.

Policy context

We consciously decided at the beginning of the project not to invite the policy sector to our stakeholder board to avoid that policy makers dominate the discourse (taking into account that the education sector is highly centralised and dominated by top-down decisions). Nevertheless, two of our board members worked previously in education policy, therefore they could provide an insider perspective. During the workshop we reflected on the possibilities of whether this project can have a policy

influence. Participants agreed that considering the current situation (i.e., the level of centralization), there is not much chance to achieve policy impact through a bottom-up initiative, but it is still worth trying by disseminating recommendations and best practices, targeting them through school communities. They also suggested sharing the results of this case study with some policy experts.

Objective of the Workshop

The main aim was to present some of our findings on transformative change in biodiversity education, with a focus on a school garden initiative in a Hungarian secondary school, as part of our broader transformative change story.

Workshop Agenda Overview

Introduction and Welcome – 5 minutes

Transformative Change Story – 45–50 minutes

- Presentation (Karmen) – 15–20 minutes
- Discussion: Questions from the Board – 30 minutes

Other Business – 30 minutes

- Lesson plan
- Special Issue article
- New article (in Hungarian)
- Dissemination: Physical format? Where, in what form, and for whom?

Closing and Farewell – 5–10 minutes

Findings

This section of findings is structured in three parts. First, we present the validated elements – the key outcomes we aimed to confirm. Second, we outline suggestions for improvement, based on the research process and its results. Third, we highlight emerging topics that warrant further attention.

Validated Elements

Storyline for the infographic

Co-Creating a School Garden: A Transformative Journey

1. Seeding the idea

A local secondary school teams up with researchers to transform an abandoned green area next to the school into a school garden. Funding is secured through a European research call.

Key elements: partnership, funding

2. **The lighthouse teacher**

A passionate teacher takes the initiative and dedicates a huge part of her time coordinating the project, collaborating with researchers, and engaging students along with her colleagues.

Key elements: dedicated teacher, teamwork

3. **Co-creating the garden**

Researchers regularly visit the school to kick in the co-creation process. They share knowledge about biodiversity, while learning from students' perspectives on nature and their ideas about how to improve the garden.

Key elements: mutual learning

4. **Growing ownership & values**

Students spend more time outdoors and take care of the garden, while developing ownership over it, and cultivating nature- and community-related values.

Key elements: engagement, hands-on learning

5. **Transforming the school**

As the garden becomes part of the school's everyday life, organisational practices start to emerge that change not only the school's surroundings, but also the mind- and skillsets of students, teachers, and researchers alike.

Key elements: institutional change, shift in mindsets

6. **Nurturing values & behaviour**

Intervention methods – such as arts-based approaches and reflexive learning – are applied to explore how the garden influences values and behaviors. Through open discussion, creative expression, and self-reflection, they deepen students' connection to nature and cultivate a shared understanding of sustainability.

Key elements: reflexive learning, arts-based methods

7. **Cultivating a bright future**

Over the years, the garden flourishes, drawing many children closer to nature, while contributing to research on nature connectedness and the related values.

Key elements: lasting transformation, long-term engagement, new research insights

Guidance for school communities: What can you do as a teacher, student or parent?

- Learn from "lighthouse teachers" and their best practices in biodiversity education.
- Help in connecting to peer-learning networks (e.g. the Hungarian Foundation for School Gardens) to support teachers in implementing school gardens and other best practices in biodiversity education.
- Encourage integrating nature-based (outdoor) learning across subjects and school community events.
- Develop biodiversity-focused experiential learning programmes that align with the curriculum while enabling creativity.
- Implement nature-based solutions in the schoolyard (e.g. birdhouses, insect hotels, wildflower meadows) that can become tools for observation and mutual learning.
- Foster a deeper connection to nature among students through hands-on learning methods, leading to long-term behavioural change.

- Engage parents and local communities in school garden activities, fostering intergenerational learning and strengthening community ties. This may also encourage sustainable food practices at home and inspire community gardens.

Guidance for NGOs and researchers: What can science and civil society do?

- Develop, disseminate and provide related teaching materials, toolkits, and trainings.
- Help in connecting to peer-learning networks (e.g. the Hungarian Foundation for School Gardens) to support teachers in implementing school gardens and other best practices in biodiversity education.
- Engage parents and local communities in school garden activities, fostering intergenerational learning and strengthening community ties. This may also encourage sustainable food practices at home and inspire community gardens.
- Create partnerships with local farmers, conservationists, and businesses to strengthen sustainable school gardens. Municipal and NGO support can provide resources, knowledge, and financial backing to maintain and expand school gardens.

Guidance for policymakers: How can you help from the policy side?

- Encourage integrating nature-based (outdoor) learning across subjects and school community events.
- Encourage and expand participatory projects – either through action research or community initiatives – to include more schools, allowing students to co-create their learning environments.
- Integrate biodiversity education across all subjects and grades to support a holistic worldview, rather than limiting it to specific age groups and disciplines.

Guidance for local communities: How can you help if you live and/or work in the school neighbourhood?

- Engage parents and local communities in school garden activities, fostering intergenerational learning and strengthening community ties. This may also encourage sustainable food practices at home and inspire community gardens.
- Create partnerships with local farmers, conservationists, and businesses to strengthen sustainable school gardens. Municipal and NGO support can provide resources, knowledge, and financial backing to maintain and expand school gardens.

Suggestions for Improvement

- Clarify more explicitly why this is valuable for teachers.
- Include concrete details and practical guidance on the significance of outdoor learning and nature connectedness – for example, highlight any changes made within schools, e.g. the establishment of working groups.

- Place stronger emphasis on biodiversity and provide specific, actionable recommendations – such as biodiversity-enhancing initiatives that can be implemented in schools.
- Highlight how school gardens and increased interaction with nature can lead to long-term behavioural change.
- The focus has become too narrow, reducing the essence and overlooking many of our key achievements – therefore, broaden the scope. Incorporate images and quotations from the research and place greater emphasis on arts-based methods.
- Parents should also be addressed, as their support and engagement are crucial.
- Include QR codes on the printed materials.
- Central curricula alone are insufficient to drive reform – local initiatives can play a key role. Engage schools directly and aim to influence education policy through that.

Emerging Topics

The feedback highlighted several key areas that require stronger emphasis and refinement in our reporting and dissemination efforts. First, it is essential to more clearly articulate the value and relevance of the project for teachers, supported by practical examples and advice. The importance of outdoor learning and connecting with nature should be underlined through concrete school-based changes, such as the formation of working groups or the redesign of learning environments.

There is a growing need to prioritise biodiversity within the narrative, including the presentation of specific, school-level programmes that promote ecological awareness and action. Moreover, the long-term behavioural impact of initiatives like school gardens and regular engagement with nature should be emphasised.

Concerns have been raised about the narrowing of focus, which can fail to address broader achievements and core messages. Therefore, the content should be expanded to reflect the full scope of results, with greater integration of visual elements, artistic methods, and quotations from the research to strengthen engagement and authenticity.

Parental and policy involvement also emerged as critical factors in ensuring the sustainability and success of these efforts; future materials should therefore address and include this audience. Practical improvements, such as the addition of QR codes on printed materials, can also support accessibility and information sharing. To address education policy, locally driven initiatives hold considerable potential. Active engagement with schools could lead to influencing education policy at a broader level and ensure lasting impact.

Conclusions and next steps

Based on the suggestions, we implemented the following improvements in our transformative change story and its dissemination:

- **Include tailored materials for teachers** that clearly demonstrate the practical value of outdoor and nature-based learning, such as examples of successful implementation and concrete benefits.
- **Integrate biodiversity-focused content** into materials, providing specific suggestions for school-level programmes that support ecological knowledge and action.
- **Broaden the narrative** to reflect the research's full scope and impact, incorporating visual storytelling, arts-based methods, and direct quotes from the research.
- **Target the whole school community, including parents**, highlighting how they can support and benefit from nature-based educational initiatives, thereby fostering wider community engagement.
- **Design and distribute the printed materials with embedded QR codes**, linking to further resources, project updates, and examples of best practices.
- **Strengthen collaboration with schools**, identifying opportunities for scaling up through local initiatives that have the potential to inform and improve education policy.

Statement on data availability

Data used to produce this report included notes taken by the authors of this report during the hybrid workshop, and the materials created throughout the research process.

Statement on ethics

This report does not include pictures from the workshop's participants, nor their names. Thus, we followed the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union (EU). The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.